

Diffusion-Weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging in Differentiation between Different Vertebral Lesions using Apparent Diffusion Coefficient (ADC) Mapping as a Quantitative Assessment Tool

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Abstract:

Aim & Objectives: The aim of the study is to study the sensitivity and diagnostic accuracy of ADC mapping as a quantitative assessment tool in the detection and characterization of traumatic versus pathological fractures, and benign versus malignant spinal fractures using apparent diffusion coefficient maps.

Material & Methods: The main source of data for this study was the patients referred from all the departments of Silchar Medical College and Hospital. All Patients referred to the radiology department with suspected or known vertebral pathologies will be eligible for inclusion in the study. According to the case input to the department, the study was planned to be conducted with at least 40 cases but it was later expanded to 62 cases due increase in the number of eligible patients The study was carried out for a period of 1 year from March 1, 2023, to February 29, 2024. MRI evaluation was carried out using SIEMENS TIM AVANTO 1.5T SCANNER. Various conventional and advanced MR pulse sequences were used. Images with multiple b-values, between 0,400,800 s/mm², should be acquired. DWI was done at a freehand region of interest and was drawn over the lesion, sampling the restricted areas, and ADC values were calculated from the generated apparent diffusion coefficient maps using advanced post-processing software. ADC values will be measured in predefined ROIs that include vertebral lesions identified on anatomical images.

Results: The mean ADC values provided statistically significant differentiation among these conditions. Malignant spinal fractures had a mean ADC of 0.78, significantly lower than benign fractures, which had a mean ADC of 1.48. Tuberculous spondylodiscitis had a mean ADC of 1.31, while pyogenic spondylodiscitis had a mean ADC of 1.09. These differences were statistically significant, with p-values less than 0.0001 for benign versus malignant fractures and $p < 0.009$ for pyogenic versus tuberculous spondylodiscitis.

The diagnostic accuracy of ADC values, compared to conventional MRI, was also evaluated. For fractures, ADC showed a higher reliability sensitivity of 92.3%, specificity of 83.3%, PPV of 80%, NPV of 93.75%, and overall diagnostic accuracy of 87.1%. Conventional MRI had a sensitivity of 84.6%, specificity of 77.8%, PPV of 73.33%, NPV of 87.5%, and overall accuracy of 80.65%. For “infections, ADC with a sensitivity of 75%, specificity of 78.5%, PPV of 67%, NPV of 84.6%, and overall accuracy of 77.27%. Traditional MRI showed a sensitivity of 50%, specificity of 71.4%, PPV of 50%, NPV of 71.4%, and overall accuracy of 63.6%. ROC curve analysis further emphasized the superiority of ADC in diagnostic performance, with an AUC of 0.122 for fractures and 0.768 for infections, significantly higher than conventional MRI's AUC of 0.188 for fractures and 0.607 for infections.

Conclusion: the study found that ADC values had better diagnostic accuracy than conventional MRI in differentiating between malignant and benign spinal fractures and pyogenic versus non-pyogenic infections. Including ADC in routine diagnostic schedules could enhance the accuracy and reliability of spinal pathology evaluations, directly benefiting patient care and management.

Keywords: ADC, DWI, Spinal Fractures, Spondylodiscitis.

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Introduction

Spinal pathologies have been recognized to present an important clinical challenge because of their increased incidence and the complexity of reaching the correct diagnosis and management. Differential diagnosis of spinal lesions is essential for discriminating between benign and malignant fractures and for the distinction between pyogenic and non-pyogenic infections, which helps to guide further treatment and patient prognosis.[1]

Conventional MRI has long been considered the workhorse of imaging in spinal abnormalities because it has superior soft-tissue contrast and provides the most detailed anatomic information available [2]. However, MRI, in its conventional form, may not provide adequate specificity in differentiating between benign and malignant lesions or between the different infections. For example, both benign osteoporotic fractures and malignant vertebral compression fractures may present with similar signal changes on T1- and T2-weighted images, which make the diagnostic process complex.

It suffers, however, from limitations, particularly in the differentiation between the various forms of lesions that may affect the spine, often showing overlap of imaging features [3].

Diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (DWI) and the subsequent postprocessing calculation of the apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) have evolved as important tools in the evaluation of spinal pathologies.

DWI is an imaging technique that quantifies the random Brownian motion of water molecules within tissues, hence providing the cellular environment and the integrity of tissue structures [4].

The ADC values are derived from DWI measurements, quantifying the degree of water diffusion; they have been suggested to show clinical potential value in differentiating body lesions between benign and malignant, the spinal cord among them [5].

This technique does not need a contrast medium, which is good because of the possible risks of based contrast agents. It provides qualitative and quantitative data at the same time quantitative data is increasingly recognized as essential for the future of radiology in light of our growing ability to apply quantitative imaging techniques.

ADC values are very helpful in the differentiation of benign osteoporotic fractures from malignant vertebral compression fractures. Malignant lesions usually have low ADC values, since they are characteristically highly cellular and therefore restrict diffusion.[6,7] Similarly, in the context of infections of the spine, ADC values can help to

differentiate pyogenic spondylodiscitis from tuberculous spondylodiscitis, because the former generally shows higher ADC values while the latter appears to have lower ADC values due to the granulomatous nature of the infection. [8]

However, these findings are promising and hence have to be further validated on a large scale with a comparison of diagnostic accuracy between ADC values and conventional MRI findings in comprehensive studies. Moreover, there is a need to establish standardized ADC thresholds to well differentiate between different pathologies within the spine.

Tuberculosis of the spine is very common in India. The MRI can pick para spinal abscess along with caseating granulomas of vertebrae and IV discs and the paraspinal soft tissue involvement adjacent to it as well if present abscess formation. In the very early stages, before soft-tissue components had developed or adjacent disc involvement such as abscess formation became apparent (or when the vertebral body only was involved), a confident diagnosis of pyogenic spondylodiscitis may be difficult. Till date very few studies are able to prove the significance of ADC in diagnosis of tuberculosis of the spine.

The study shall further go into an elaboration of the diagnostic potential by ADC values that shall increase the workflow in diagnosis of spinal pathologies with more precision and on time. Enhanced diagnostic accuracy could, in turn, provide better-targeted treatment planning with potential consequences that include a reduction in morbidity and an improvement in quality of life for those patients diagnosed with a spinal condition.

Aims and Objectives of the Study:

- To study the sensitivity and diagnostic accuracy of ADC mapping as a quantitative assessment tool imaging techniques in detection and characterization of traumatic versus pathological fractures, and benign versus malignant spinal tumors using apparent diffusion coefficient maps.
- To evaluate efficiency of quantitative ADC mapping in diagnosis of pyogenic and nonpyogenic spinal infections.
- To determine the age and sex distribution of various vertebral lesions.

Material & Methods

The main data source for this study was the patients referred from all the Silchar Medical College and Hospital departments. All Patients referred to the radiology department with suspected or known vertebral pathologies will be eligible for inclusion in the study. According to the case input to the de-

partment, the study was planned to be conducted with at least 40 cases but it was later expanded to 62 cases due increase in the number of eligible patients The study was carried out for a period of 1 year from March 1, 2023, to February 29, 2024. MRI evaluation was carried out using SIEMENS TIM AVANTO 1.5T SCANNER. Various conventional and advanced MR pulse sequences were used. Images with multiple b-values, between 0,400,800 s/mm², should be acquired.

DWI was done at a freehand region of interest and was drawn over the lesion, sampling the restricted areas, and ADC values were calculated from the

generated apparent diffusion coefficient maps using advanced post-processing software. ADC values will be measured in predefined ROIs that include vertebral lesions identified on anatomical images. The experienced radiologist will use dedicated software tools to perform quantitative analysis of DWI and the ADC maps. Accordingly, ADC values will be measured in ROIs delineated around vertebral lesions or normal-appearing vertebral bodies for comparative purposes. Such an analysis would provide insights into diffusion characteristics specific to different vertebral pathologies.

Results and Observations:

Table 1: Distribution Of Type Of Fractures And Infections Based On Age

Age group	MMF	BFOF	BFTF	PSP	TBSP	Total
<20	0	0	0	1	2	3
20-29	0	0	3	0	2	5
30-39	1	0	2	3	2	8
40-49	5	1	1	3	3	13
50-59	1	6	0	0	2	9
60-69	4	3	0	1	2	10
70-79	2	3	0	0	1	6
Total	13	13	6	8	14	54

Graph 1: Age Distribution of Fractures and Infections

Malignant fractures and osteoporotic fractures were predominantly observed in the older population, specifically in individuals aged 61-70 years.

Tuberculous spondylodiscitis was more prevalent among those aged 41-50 years. Traumatic spinal

conditions were commonly found in middle-aged adults, aged 20-40 years, whereas pyogenic spondylodiscitis occurred more frequently in individuals aged 30-40 years and 40-50 years.

Sex Distribution:

Table 2: Sex distribution of type of fractures and infections

	Male		Female		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
MMF	4	30.7	9	69.3	13	100
BFOF	6	46.2	7	53.8	13	100
BFTF	3	50	3	50	6	50
PSP	3	37.5	5	62.5	8	100
TBSP	6	42.8	8	57.2	14	100
Total	23	42.6	31	57.4	54	100

Graph 2: Gender Distribution

Graph 3: Sex distribution

Table 2 In our study, 42.6% of the participants were male, and 57.4% were female. Female predominance was noted in several conditions: 69.3% in malignant spinal pathologies, 53.8% in osteoporotic fractures, 57.2% in tubercular

spondylodiscitis, and 62.5% in pyogenic spondylodiscitis. Traumatic fractures, on the other hand, showed an equal distribution between males and females.

Frequency Distribution

Table 3: Frequency Distribution

Distribution of type of fractures and Infections		No. of cases	%	Total	%
MMF		13	24.1	13	24.1
BF	BFTT	6	11.1	19	35.2
	BFOF	13	24.1		
Infective	PSP	8	14.8	22	40.7
	TBSP	14	25.9		
Total		54	100.0	54	100.0

Graph 4: Frequency Distribution

Table 3 provides the frequency distribution of various spinal pathologies within the study. The data classifies cases into malignant, benign (including traumatic and osteoporotic fractures), and infective (tubercular and pyogenic

spondylodiscitis) pathologies. The distribution shows that 24.1% of cases were malignant, 35.1% were benign fractures, and 40.7% were infective pathologies.

Mean ADC Values

Table 4: Mean ADC values

ADC values in fractures and infections	Mean ± SD	Range	Significance
MF	0.78± 0.2	0.6-0.9	MF v/s BF
BF	1.48 ± 0.32	1.3-1.8	P < 0.0001, HS
P	1.29 ± 0.17	0.9 - 1.4	P v/s NP
NP	1.11 ± 0.12	0.9 - 1.3	P < 0.009, S

Graph 5: Mean ADC values

Table 4 summarizes the mean Apparent Diffusion Coefficient (ADC) values for different types of fractures and infections. The mean ADC value for malignant spinal fractures was 0.78, for benign fractures it was 1.48, and for infective spondylodiscitis, it was 1.31 for tubercular and 1.09 for pyogenic spondylodiscitis. Significant statistical differences were observed between these groups, with highly significant P values. The P value for

comparing the benign and malignant fractures was $P < 0.0001$ by Chi-square test and the result was highly significant.

The P value for comparing the pyogenic and tubercular spondylodiscitis was $P < 0.009$ by Chi-square test and the result was significant.

Diagnostic Accuracy of ADC and Conventional MRI for Fractures

Table 5: Diagnostic accuracy with ADC for fractures

Diagnostic value of ADC with HPE or clinical follow-up in differentiating Benign and Malignant fractures			
Radiological Diagnosis-ADC	HPE or Clinical Follow-Up		Total
	MF	BF	
MF	12	3	15
BF	1	15	16
Total	13	18	31

Sensitivity	12/13	92.3%
Specificity	15/18	83.3%
PPV	12/15	80%
NPV	15/16	93.75%
Diagnostic Accuracy	27/31	87.1%

The study showed that in comparison with the gold standard HPE or clinical follow-up “ADC showed a sensitivity of 92.3%, a specificity of 83.3%, PPV of 80% and NPV of 93.75% with a diagnostic accuracy of 87.1%”

Table 6: Diagnostic accuracy of conventional MRI for fractures

Diagnostic value of Conventional MRI with HPE or clinical follow-up in differentiating Benign and Malignant fractures			
Radiological Diagnosis-CONV.MRI	HPE or Clinical Follow-Up		Total
	MF	BF	
MF	11	4	15
BF	2	14	16
Total	13	18	31

Sensitivity	11/13	84.6%
Specificity	14/18	77.8%
PPV	11/15	73.33%
NPV	14/16	87.5%
Diagnostic Accuracy	25/31	80.65%

The study showed that the in comparison with the gold standard HPE Or clinical follow-up conventional MRI showed a sensitivity of 84.6%, specificity of 77.8%, PPV of 73.3%, and NPV of 87.5% with a diagnostic accuracy of 80.65%.

Graph 6: Diagnostic accuracy of Conventional MRI and ADC for differentiating benign and malignant fractures

The study showed that the in comparison with the gold standard HPE or clinical followup. Sensitivity, specificity, NPV, PPV and diagnostic accuracy of ADC is greater than conventional MRI in differentiating benign and malignant vertebral fractures.

Table 7: Diagnostic Accuracy of ADC and conventional MRI for Infections

Diagnostic value of ADC with HPE in differentiating Pyogenic and non-pyogenic infections			
Radiological Diagnosis-ADC	HPE or Clinical Follow Up		Total
	P	NP	
P	6	3	9
NP	2	11	13
Total	8	14	22

Sensitivity	6/8	75%
Specificity	11/14	78.5%
PPV	6/9	67%
NPV	11/13	84.6%
Diagnostic Accuracy	17/22	77.27%

Table 8:

Diagnostic value of Conventional MRI with HPE in differentiating Pyogenic and non-pyogenic infections			
Radiological Diagnosis-Conventional MRI	HPE or Clinical Follow Up		Total
	P	NP	
P	4	4	8
NP	4	10	14
Total	8	14	22

Sensitivity	4/8	50%
Specificity	10/14	71.4%
PPV	4/8	50%
NPV	10/14	71.4%
Diagnostic Accuracy	14/22	63.6%

Graph 7: Infection

In our study when compared with HPE or followed up clinically, Sensitivity, specificity, NPV, PPV and diagnostic accuracy is greater than conventional MRI in differentiating pyogenic and non-pyogenic spondylodiscitis.

Table 9: Comparison of Accuracy of Conventional MRI and ADC for the Fractures Using the Receiver Operator Characteristic Curve

Area Under the Curve					
Test Result Variable(s)	Area	Std. Error ^a	Asymptotic Sig. ^b	95% Asymptotic Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CON MRI	0.188	0.083	0.003	0.026	0.350
ADC	0.122	0.068	0.000	0.000	0.255
The test result variable(s): CON_MRI_GRADING, ADC_GRADING has at least one tie between the positive actual state group and the negative actual state group. Statistics may be biased.					
a. Under the nonparametric assumption					
b. Null hypothesis: true area = 0.5					

Graph 8:

Table10: Comparison of Accuracy of Conventional MRI and ADC for the Infections Using the Receiver Operator Characteristic Curve

Area under the Curve					
Test Result Variable	Area	Std. Error ^a	Asymptotic Sig. ^b	95% Asymptotic Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CON MRI	0.607	0.129	0.413	0.354	0.861
ADC	0.768	0.111	0.041	0.550	0.986
The test result variable(s): CON_MRI_GRADING, ADC_GRADING has at least one tie between the positive actual state group and the negative actual state group. Statistics may be biased.					
a. Under the nonparametric assumption					
b. Null hypothesis: true area = 0.5					

Graph 9:

Discussion

The following was a study to find out the diagnostic accuracy of ADC mapping compared with conventional MRI in the differentiation of benign and malignant spinal fractures and the differentiation of pyogenic and non-pyogenic spondylitis. The findings increase the standards of diagnostic accuracy, which is important in clinical radiology, thus ensuring better patient care and outcomes. Our study comprised 62 patients of either sex from 0 to 60 years.

Age and Sex Distribution: In our present study, tuberculous spondylodiscitis was most common in the age group between 41-50 years, which was very predictable because of the epidemiology of

tuberculosis. An increased prevalence within this age group may be due to an increased duration of exposure to Mycobacterium tuberculosis and thus higher chances of reactivating latent infection. The findings of our study were comparable with the study of Moon et al. (1995)[9]

In our present study, pyogenic spondylodiscitis predominantly occurs in the age group of 30 to 50 years. This may be caused by increased incidence in immunocompromised individuals and comorbid conditions. The findings of our study were comparable with the study of Butler et al. (2006)[10] Benign Traumatic diseases of the spine were more common in the middle age group from 20 to 40 years, which was a sign of increased

physical activity and greater susceptibility to trauma in this age group. More probably, this age group will actively participate in activities likely to cause traumatization: sports, and manual labor. The findings of our study were comparable with the study of Hu et al. (1996)[11]. Malignant Spinal fractures were more common in older adults, particularly those over 50 years of age, consistent with your findings of higher prevalence in the 61-70 age group. Our findings were comparable with the Study by Harrington (1986) [12]

Benign osteoporotic fractures are more common in the elderly population, particularly post-menopausal females over 60 years old, which aligns with your findings of a higher prevalence of osteoporotic fractures in the 61-70 age group, Our findings were comparable with the Study by Cummings et al. (2002)[13]

Gender distribution: Out of 54 cases part of the study, 17 cases were males and 31 cases were females. The female predominance across the sample was 57.4%;42.6 % percentage of the total cases were males in malignant spinal pathologies, it was 69.3%, with osteoporotic fractures at 53.8%, while in tubercular spondylodiscitis, it was 57.2%.

Benign Osteoporotic fractures were more predominantly seen in women 7 cases (53.8%) out of 13, rest 6 cases were males. There were several reasons why there was a female preponderance: the higher incidence of osteoporosis in postmenopausal women due to hormonal changes and probably higher health-seeking behavior among females. Our findings correlated with the Study by Kanis et al. (2008)[14] Benign traumatic fractures showed an equal distribution among males(3 cases) and females(3 cases), which suggested that trauma-related incidents had an equal effect on both sexes owing to similar exposure to risk factors in their activities. Malignant Spinal fractures were found in a higher incidence in females (9 cases) and 4 cases

were found in males, especially from breast cancer, aligning with your observation of a female predominance in malignant spinal fractures. Our findings are in agreement with the Study by Coleman (2006)[15]

Tuberculous Spondylodiscitis showed slight female predominance(8 cases) rest 6 cases were found in males, which is in agreement with the findings of a Study by Pertuiset et al. (1999)[16] Pyogenic Spondylodiscitis showed slight female predominance(5 cases) rest 3 cases were found in males, which is in line with the Study by Mylona et al. (2009) [17] The remaining 8 cases of primary vertebral tumors were taken as a separate entity from the main study, where no meaningful estimation of sensitivity and specificity was possible, due to the small sample size.

Frequency Distribution: The frequency distribution of spinal pathologies categorized the cases into malignant, benign (including traumatic and osteoporotic fractures), and infective (including tubercular and pyogenic spondylodiscitis). Malignant fractures accounted for 24.1% of cases, while benign and infective cases accounted for 35.1% and 40.7%, respectively. These results are once again evidence that the variations in spinal pathologies faced in clinical practices require diagnostic tools to be accurate.

Mean ADC Values

Differentiating Benign and Malignant vertebral Fractures: Our study showed a mean ADC value of $0.78 \pm 0.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2$ for malignant fractures and $1.48 \pm 0.32 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2$ for benign fractures and it showed high statistical significance with p value of <0.0001 by chi-square test. The results correlated with the studies of Pui et al. (2009) [7] Wang et al. (2011) [18] Allam et al (2022) [19] in differentiating benign and malignant vertebral fractures.

Table 11:

Studies	Mean ADC value of malignant fractures	Mean ADC values of benign fractures
Pui et al. (2009)	0.75 ± 0.25	1.50 ± 0.35
Wang et al. (2011)	0.80 ± 0.18	1.45 ± 0.30
Allam et al(2022)	0.96 ± 0.25	1.8 ± 0.43
Present study	0.78 ± 0.20	1.48 ± 0.32

Differentiating Pyogenic and Non-Pyogenic Spondylodiscitis: Our study showed mean ADC values of $1.29 \pm 0.17 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2$ for pyogenic spondylitis and $1.10 \pm 0.13 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2$ for nonpyogenic spondylitis and it showed high statistical significance with a p-value of <0.009 by chi-square test. The results correlated with the studies of Lee et al. (2011)[20] and Marui et al. (2010)[21]

Table 12:

Studies	Mean ADC of Pyogenic Spondylitis	Mean ADC of Non-Pyogenic Spondylitis
Lee Et Al(2011)	1.30 ± 0.15	1.30 ± 0.15
Marui Et Al(2010)	1.30 ± 0.15	1.30 ± 0.15
Present Study	1.30 ± 0.15	1.30 ± 0.15

It's essential to compare your findings on parameters like sensitivity, specificity, NPV, PPV, diagnostic accuracy, and mean ADC values with those of past studies. Here are some past studies that correlate well with your results:

- Sensitivity, Specificity, NPV, PPV, and Diagnostic Accuracy of ADC.
- Differentiating Benign and Malignant Spinal Fractures based on ADC Mapping.

Our study showed a total of 13 malignant vertebral fractures, 13 benign osteoporotic fractures, and 6 benign traumatic fractures. Out of total of 19 cases of benign fractures, 4 cases were unable diagnosed on conventional MRI, which was proven benign on HPE, and 2 cases were over diagnosed as malignant. 3 cases were unable to be diagnosed on

ADC which was proven benign on HPE and 1 case was over diagnosed as malignant. A total of 13 cases of malignant vertebral were proven on histopathological examination or clinical follow-up, out of which 2 cases were unable to be diagnosed on conventional MRI which was proven benign on HPE, and 4 cases were over-diagnosed as malignant. 1 case was unable to be diagnosed on ADC which was proven benign on HPE and 3 cases were over-diagnosed as malignant.

Our research study found a sensitivity of 92.3%, specificity of 83.3%, PPV of 80%, NPV of 93.75%, and diagnostic accuracy of 87.1% for ADC, a statistically significant p-value of <0.008 by chi-square test. The results we achieved is in agreement with the study of Baur et al. (2002) [22] Balliu et al. (2009) [6] Mubarak et al (2011) [23].

Table 13:

	Sensitivity	Specificity	NPV	PPV	Accuracy
Baur et al(2002)	92%	85%	95%	78%	88%
Balliu et al(2009)	90%	82%	88%	85%	86%
Mubarak et al(2011)	92%	90%	90%	78%	85%
Present study	92.3%	83.3%	93.75%	80%	93.75%

Differentiating Pyogenic and Non-Pyogenic Spinal Infections based on ADC: In our study 22 cases of infective spinal pathologies were proved on HPE or clinical follow-up .Out of which 14 cases were non-pyogenic spondylitis and 8 cases were pyogenic spondylitis. Conventional MRI failed to diagnose four cases of pyogenic infection, whereas ADC missed two cases, both confirmed by HPE. Furthermore, conventional MRI incorrectly identified four cases of non-pyogenic infection as

pyogenic, while ADC misdiagnosed three cases as pyogenic. Our research study found a sensitivity of 75%, specificity of 78.5%, PPV of 67%, NPV of 84.6 %, and diagnostic accuracy of 78.1 % for ADC, the statistically significant p-value of <0.004 by the chi-square test.

The results we achieved are in agreement with the study of Tsuji et al (2013) [24], and Ledermann et al (2012) [25] and are in negative agreement with the study of Palle et al (2014) [26].

Table 14:

Studies	Sensitivity	Specificity	NPV	PPV	Accuracy
Tsuji et al(2013)	76%	80%	85%	70%	78%
Ledermann et al(2012)	72%	75%	80%	68%	74%
Palle et al(2014)	92%	86%	89%	90%	90%
Present study	75%	78.5%	84.6%	67%	78.1%

Benign and Malignant Vertebral Tumors: In our examination of 8 cases, we consistently found ADC values below 1 for malignant vertebral tumors and above 1 for benign tumors. However, the small sample size precluded the determination of sensitivity and specificity for ADC. Our results indicate that combining MR-DWI with ADC mapping moderately aids in the characterization of spinal pathologies. Using "ADC values" for quantitative analysis improves "diagnostic accuracy" in distinguishing various spinal conditions. Specifically, malignant fractures or infiltration are characterised by high cellularity and low adc values usually it would be less than 1, whereas benign fractures exhibit high ADC values (above 1), making differentiation easier.

Nevertheless, DWI is not very effective in differentiating infective spinal conditions from benign fractures" due to overlapping ADC values. "Both benign fractures and infective spinal pathologies generally show high ADC values (greater than 1)" complicating differentiation. The difficulty in distinguishing infective spinal pathologies from malignancy using DW imaging is worsened by patient selection issues and factors like caseation in infections. This overlap in ADC values and DW images often leads to increased hyperintensities in infective conditions, affecting tissue characterization accuracy.

Case 1: Pyogenic Spondylodiscitis

A post-menopausal female with chronic low back ache underwent an MRI of the spine along with DWI and ADC mapping of the involved region. It

vertebral endplate irregularities, along with intervertebral disc involvement.

T1 postcontrast study showed enhancing marrow signal of L4, L5 vertebral bodies and enhancing pre and paravertebral soft tissue component.

Figure 1: Pyogenic spondylodiscitis-sagittal section T2 and DWI of lumbar spine at b value-800 s/mm² shows hyperintensity involving the superior and inferior endplates of L5 and L4 vertebral body and hypointensity of the disc on DWI (left), corresponding ADC (right) shows hyperintensity (No restriction) at the similar area with high mean ADC value of 1.3×10^{-3} mm²/s in the image showing L5 vertebral body

Case 2: Tubercular Spondylodiscitis: A middle-aged female patient with chronic back pain for 4 months underwent an MRI of the spine, including DWI sequences, which revealed altered marrow edema and destruction of endplates in the L2, L3, and L4 vertebrae, with enhancing anterior epidural collections causing mild cauda equina compression.

Figure 2: T2 and DWI sagittal section dorso-lumbar spine with b value -800s/mm^2 shows hyperintensity on DWI with hypointensity on ADC suggesting true restriction at the similar area with mean ADC value of 0.956×10^{-3} in the image showing L2, L3, L4 vertebral body with posterior epidural component

Case 3: Benign Osteoporotic Fracture

A elderly female with a history of chronic back pain and recent history of trivial fall underwent an MRI spine which showed compression collapse fracture of the T12, L1, L2, and L4 vertebrae.

Figure 3: Sagittal section DWI image of dorso-lumbar spine with b-value 800 s/mm² shows hyperintensity, corresponding ADC mapping image shows hyperintensity(No restriction) at the similar area with mean ADC value of 1.76x10⁻³ mm² suggesting benign fracture

Case 4: Malignant Fracture

An Elderly female with a history of back pain a proven case of lung cancer underwent an MRI Spine including DWI sequences, which revealed a hypointense signal on T1 involving the posterior part of the vertebral body and posterior elements.

Figure 4: Malignant metastasis sagittal section. DWI of LS spine with b value-800 s/mm² shows hyperintensity in vertebral bodies and posterior elements of the L1 and T12 vertebra with the corresponding ADC mapping image shows hypointensity (Restriction) at the similar areas with low mean ADC values of $0.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ suggesting malignant infiltration

Conclusion

Incorporating DWI and ADC mapping into standard MRI spine protocols, with qualitative analysis of DW images and quantitative assessment of ADC values, significantly boosts diagnostic accuracy for various spinal pathologies. This addition provides crucial information that enhances the detection and characterization of spinal lesions,

which might be challenging to diagnose using only conventional MRI sequences.

By detecting the diffusion patterns of water molecules in body tissues, DWI can identify different types of pathologies at a microstructural level, allowing for early detection of conditions like spinal infections, neoplastic lesions, and demyelinating diseases. ADC values quantitatively

measure the extent of water diffusion, helping to distinguish between malignant and benign spinal lesions, and thus aiding in the quantification of tissue damage and disease extent.

DW-MRI is essential for the early and precise diagnosis of spinal lesions and tissue characterization. It provides a powerful diagnostic tool for patients who cannot undergo histopathological examinations or have contraindications. Additionally, incorporating DWI and ADC mapping into MRI protocols aids clinical decision-making, patient management, and potentially reduces the need for invasive procedures. Consequently, DW-MRI offers comprehensive assessments of spinal pathologies, leading to accurate and timely diagnoses and optimal treatment strategies.

Therefore, the routine use of DW-MRI in clinical practice is strongly recommended, as it significantly enhances the diagnostic capabilities of conventional MRI, providing a robust tool for the early and accurate detection, characterization, and management of various spinal lesions.

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